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Research Article

**EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT OF ALLAMA IQBAL
MEMORIAL TEACHING HOSPITAL SIALKOT**¹Dr. Yasir Hussain, ²Dr. Noor Ul Huda, ³Dr. Mohsin Ali¹Foundation university Islamabad²Foundation University Medical College, Islamabad³Foundation University Medical College, Islamabad**Abstract:**

Objective: to consider the example of the surgical procedures in the emergency unit of the memory teaching of Allama Iqbal, Sialkot.

Study design: descriptive / observational examination

Place and duration of the study: This test was conducted at the Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital teaching, Sialkot, July 2015 for July 2016.

Materials and methods: 910 surgical procedures have been associated with this review. All surgical procedures were included, despite the fact that the cases were transferred to different divisions and those who came out in opposition to the direction of restoration were discarded. Ages, gender, area, type of surgical procedures, were noted in the Performa described. The consent of the foundation's ethics committee was taken. The information was inspected on Form 10 of the SSPS.

Results: In this research, the recurrences of the surgical process the emergency unit was more extreme (42.41 percent) 386 cases at the age of 15-25 years and lower (0.21%) two cases at the age of 90 years or more as they appeared in table n.01. There were (56.70 percent) 516 cases of men and (43.29 percent) 394 cases of women as they appeared in table no. 02. Surgery patients of the city's population were (65 percent) and 588 cases (35 percent) 322 cases of field populations, as shown in Table No.03. Recurrence of the OA state in the main case (20.11 percent) 102 cases in men and (15.27 percent) 139 cases of women and was a basis (0.1 sec) 1 rate in case of intubation cash, repair of vascular repair ligament and exploratory laparotomy for launching a weapon in female patients as shown in table n. 04. There were (10 percent) 91 cases of men and (9.45 percent) 86 cases of emergency evacuation of women from delicate injuries (10.10 percent) 92 cases of men and (8.13 percent) 74 cases of women at the event Processes cutting and disposal research laparotomy for typhoid puncture, duodenal ulcer, cutting and blunt lesion injury to the stomach was completed the second largest surgical emergency trial unit Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital of teaching, Sialkot, as shown in table No.04.

Conclusion: The results of this review are sound, as better emergency supplies are being developed for patients and to focus and improve the preparation of surgical individuals. The government at different stages must transmit the current logical devices for the exact preoperative conclusion of the surgical crises in primary care centers.

Key Words: Surgical Procedures, Emergency, Retrospective.

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INTRODUCTION:

A normal population in Pakistan has 173.5 million (1 July 2010) or, in other words, a rate of 2.05% per year and has a national dispersion against the urban one of 64% compared to 36% [1]. Recruited experts of drugs (principal and specialists) in Pakistan until May 31, 2010 are 142792 (119083 + 23709), which makes the extension of the main staff of the general medical procedure an essential distinctive force that oversees large volumes of emergency confirmations, its management. Consideration is of great need in the configuration of tertiary consideration and is a crucial piece to prepare the inhabitants of the surgery. There is a reliable increase in the number of emergency admissions [2] that merge surgical emergencies [3]. Many audits have seen cases of emergency hospital admissions [4,5] and emergency interventions⁶. However, there is little information available on the extent of general emergency surgery calls worldwide. and the composition aspect showed that no survey on access to the workload in Pakistan was conducted or announced. Indeed, there is a more significant pending task in the emergency surgical meeting than the one revealed by observing only the insistence and surgical activities. Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital's medical procedure agency, Sialkot includes two units of general medical procedures other than the qualities of neurosurgery and orthopedics; the workplaces of the pediatric medical procedure,

urology and the plastic medical procedure are also present. The two surgical units have 50 beds each, with the same spread of outpatients, activities and emergency days. Like the Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital, Sialkot is an open facility that also attracts patients from other low-wage neighborhoods in the city and the Sialkot National Area. Many patients have a place with a low-budget social event. The case of surgical emergencies changes with geographical positions, in different races, age meetings, social classes and people with different occupations. There are not many neighborhood tests available on the transmission of the disease, on cases of affliction and on the recurrence of a particular disease spread in the city, in the domain and in the country. This check was conducted to find the case of regulated surgical emergencies in the theater of emergency operations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

910 methods have been incorporated into this review. All surgeries were incorporated, while cases that were transferred to different offices and those that withdrew from the repairing lawyer were rejected. Age, gender, region, type of surgical interventions were recorded in the Performa described. The authorization of the organization's ethics committee has been taken. The information was examined on the adaptation 10 of the SSPS 10.

RESULTS:

Table No. 1: Age Distribution in Surgical Emergencies

Sr.No	Age (Years)	Cases	Percentage %
1	15-25	386	42.41
2	26-36	148	16.26
3	37-47	151	16.59
4	48-58	123	13.53
5	59- 69	81	8.91
6	79-89	19	2.09
7	90 & above	2	0.21
	Total	910	100

Table No. 2: Gender Distributions in Surgical Emergencies

Sr No	Gender	Cases	Percentage %
1	Male	516	56.70
2	Female	394	43.29
	Total	910	100.0

Table No. 3: Area Distributions in Surgical Emergencies

Sr No.	Area	Cases	Percentage %
1	Urban	588	65.00
2	Rural	322	35.00
	Total	910	100.0

In this investigation the occurrence of surgical crises was most extreme (42.41%) 386 cases at the age amass 15-25 years and least (0.21%) 2 cases at the age aggregate 90 10. above as appeared in table no.01. There were (56.70%) 516 cases from male and (43.29%) 394 cases from female as appeared in table no.02. The surgical crises were from urban populace (65%) 588 cases and (35%) 322 cases from provincial populaces as appeared in table no.03.

Table No.4: Type of Surgical Emergencies

Sr No	Type of Surgical Emergencies	Male (%)	Female (%)
1	Open Appendectomy (positive)	102 (11.20%)	139 (15.27%)
2	Exploratory Lapratomy for Typhoid Perforation	10 (1.1%)	5 (0.54%)
3	Excision of Soft Tissue Lesions	91 (10%)	86(9.45%)
4	Diabetic foot Debridement	36(3.95%)	25(2.74%)
5	Chest intubation	32(3.51%)	01(0.10%)
6	Tendon Repair	18(1.97%)	01(0.10%)
7	Hemostasis+ vascular repair	06(0.65%)	01(0.10%)
8	Simple Sutures	02(0.22%)	01(0.10%)
9	Exploratory Laparotomy	02(0.22%)	04(0.43%)
10	Foreign body	22(2.41%)	07(0.76%)
11	Below Knee Amputation	04(0.43%)	03(0.32%)
12	Exploratory Laparotomy for Duodenal Ulcer	12(1.31%)	06(0.65%)
13	Exploratory Lapraotomy for Gunshot	10(1.1%)	01(0.10%)
14	Exploratory Laprotomy for Stab	05(0.54%)	02(0.22%)
15	Exploratory Laprotomy for Blunt Abdominal Trauma	04(0.43%)	02(0.22%)
16	Herniorraphy	11(1.20%)	03(0.32%)
17	Excision of Carbuncle	03(0.32%)	07(0.76%)
18	Incision and Drainage	92(10.10%)	74(8.13%)
19	Debridement	51(5.60%)	29(3.18%)
	Total	513(56.37%)	397(43.62)

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The frequency of open appendectomy was 102 main cases (11.20%) in men and (15.27%) 139 cases and there was a minimum rate (0.1%) 1 in case of chest intubation, ligament, vascular repair and exploration. Laparotomy due to pistol shot in female patients, as shown in table n. 04. (10%) 91 cases of men and (9.45%) 86 cases of women of emergency extraction due to delicate lesions, (10.10%) 92 cases of men and (8.13%) 74 cases of women, if there has been an incidence. the point of entry and emergency of the waste. The exploratory laparotomy for typhoid puncture, duodenal ulcer, skin lesion and obtuse stomach injury was the second most normal crisis in the emergency surgical branch of the Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot, as shown in the table no 4.

DISCUSSION:

The consequences of this investigation showed that (half) of the cases presented in the emergency division were of a general medical procedure. The broken appendix is the most regular emergency stomach worldwide.⁷ Furthermore, in our examination, particularly later analysis is an infected appendix. The most continuous activity was appendectomy 102 (11.20%) in men and 139 (15.27%) in women. A similar model was also observed in other cities 6,8. Common activities were appendectomy (27%), infiltration of the entry point (19%), debridement (09%), laparotomy (10%), herniorrhaphy (2%), below the extraction knee (1%), repair of the ligament (2%) vascular repair (1%), extraction of wounds of delicate tissues (19.45%), diabetic foot debridement (6%) outside the body (3%) and chest intubation (4 %). The head of the injured group is the general specialist. The advanced rules and proposals and trauma life support (ATLS) of the Royal College of Surgeons of England express that a group with lesions must incorporate a general surgeon^{10,11}. However, only a minority of all patients with lesions require an assessment for the stomach and the vascular system. injuries by a specialist, with less surgery.¹² A study¹³ showed that general specialists interviewed 30.1% of patients with lesions; only 12.3% of patients were admitted by general specialists. 9.6% of patients required surgery with the agent, while 2.7% of patients received perceptions. In another study, 12 injuries included approximately 2% of the overall exceptional load surgical emergency in which specialists generally engaged in the evaluation of 25% of severely impaired patients, of which less than 10% of the patients required surgery.²¹ study 14 conducted to uncover the "unconscious" available to return to work, the remaining task of a general surgical group

showed that up to 5.5 hours of each day accessible if the need to evaluate the references was needed. These tests have reinforced our perception that there is a more obvious remaining load than the one discovered by simply discovering the surgical confirmations and activities. Another study¹⁶ examined the nighttime action of the surgical occupants and deduced that it mainly includes exercises of daily life, persistent assessment and correspondence. In addition, inform⁶¹⁷ that when the pulse is used as an indicator of physiological and psychological data consolidated stretching, the surgical occupiers manage the feelings of anxiety tachycardia "available to return to work". The inhabitants of the surgery also show an expansion in the WBC review "accessible if necessary".

CONCLUSION:

The actual remaining task that remains in the hands of a surgical emergency group available to return to work handles intense states of the stomach area with appendectomy as the most regular activity performed. The consequences of this research are useful to organize better transmission of emergency benefits for patients and to focus and improve the preparation of the surgical occupants. The government at different levels should provide the current symptomatic tools for a thorough preoperative analysis of surgical crises in open treatment centers. These measures will improve the administration and outcome of surgical crises.

Conflict of Interest: The study has no conflict of interest to announce by any writer.

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